

Higher Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based
Index is a predictor of type 2 diabetes in a German
population sample

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL
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We aim to assess the longitudinal nature of the association between higher thyroxine pituitary threshold for thyrotropin secretion inhibition, measured by the Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index (PTFQI)(1,2), and type 2 diabetes in the population-based Study of Health in Pomerania (SHIP).

The SHIP is a population-based cohort from Germany, recruited between 1997 and 2001. A follow-up examination was performed between 2002 and 2006, when a total of 3300 subjects from 4308 could be revisited. After excluding 285 subjects who took thyroid medication at baseline and 457 with missing data of variables of interest at baseline, 3566 participants were initially considered. Then, subjects with type 1 or type 2 diabetes and those without follow-up data were excluded, which filtered 2542 subjects for further analysis (Supplementary Figure 1. Flowchart of participants' selection).

The mean age was 47.7 years and 50% were men (Supplementary Table 1).

PTFQI, age-, sex-, and body mass index (BMI)- adjusted association with diabetes was estimated with Poisson regression models. Diabetes was defined at each examination as patients reporting a previous medical diagnosis of type 2 diabetes and/or taking anti-diabetic medication.

Among the 2215 euthyroid subjects, the Incidence Rate Ratios (IRR) for type 2 diabetes was higher among subjects in the 4th PTFQI quartile vs. those in the 1st one (OR 1.72; CI: 1.06, 2.86) after adjusting for age and sex (Supplementary Table 2).

We also explored, across the whole spectrum of thyroid regulation (euthyroid and non-euthyroid subjects included), the association of the TSH Index (Supplementary Table 3) and the Thyrotroph T4 Resistance Index (Supplementary Table 4) with incident type 2 diabetes, observing a statistically significant association when comparing the 4th vs. the 1st quartile of TSH Index (OR 1.80; CI: 1.14, 2.89) after adjusting for age and sex.

In addition, we excluded those subjects with abnormal values of HbA1c (baseline characteristics of the 2478 participants in Supplementary Table 5) and assessed the incidence of type 2 diabetes (Supplementary Figure 2), and, furthermore, we identified those subjects with abnormal HbA1c at follow-up not previously identified as diabetics, given that at the time of this study HbA1c was not a diagnosis criterion (Supplementary Table 6). We explored PTFQI effect on type 2 diabetes incidence across obesity strata. We observed a tendency for a progressively reduced effect at more severe obesity categories (Supplementary Figure 3).

Finally, we explored additional models considering other variables for adjustment, which could confound type 2 diabetes (Supplementary Table 7).

1. Laclaustra M, Moreno-Franco B, Lou-Bonafonte JM, Mateo-Gallego R, Casasnovas JA, Guallar-Castillon P, et al. Impaired Sensitivity to Thyroid Hormones Is Associated With Diabetes and Metabolic Syndrome. *Diabetes Care*. 2019 Feb 1;42(2):303–10.
2. Alonso-Ventura V, Civeira F, Alvarado-Rosas A, Lou-Bonafonte JM, Calmarza P, Moreno-Franco B, et al. A Cross-Sectional Study Examining the Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile Index and Its Relationship with Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases. *Thyroid*. 2022 Dec;32(12):1488–99.

Supplementary Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the sample after exclusion of baseline type 1 and type 2 diabetes and lost-to-follow-up.

	All	PTFQI quartiles				p
		1 st [min.,-0.19)	2 nd [-0.19,0.00)	3 rd [0.00,0.22)	4 th [0.22,max.]	
N	2542	636	635	637	634	
ft4 (pmol/L)	14.21(2.11)	12.78(1.22)	13.88(2.77)	14.43(1.52)	15.76(1.34)	-
ft4 (ng/dL)	1.10(0.16)	0.99(0.09)	1.08(0.22)	1.12(0.12)	1.22(0.10)	-
TSH (mIU/L)	1.09(2.73)	0.54(0.28)	1.20(4.95)	1.27(2.10)	1.33(0.74)	-
Age (years)	47.7(15.1)	49.1(14.1)	47.7(15.1)	48.2(15.4)	45.8(15.7)	<0.001
Sex (male)	50.00[1,271]	53.93[343]	48.03[305]	50.71[323]	47.32[300]	0.076
Waist circumference (cm)	88.08(13.70)	88.71(13.08)	87.39(13.69)	88.21(13.56)	88.03(14.43)	0.302
BMI (Kg/m²)	26.93(4.57)	26.92(4.30)	26.59(4.35)	26.90(4.50)	27.30(5.07)	0.110
Glucose (spot) (mmol/L)	5.36(0.96)	5.44(1.21)	5.32(0.85)	5.36(0.89)	5.31(0.86)	0.008
HbA1c (%)	5.26(0.64)	5.31(0.69)	5.22(0.60)	5.27(0.64)	5.25(0.63)	0.195

Cells show mean(sd) or percentage[count]. Statistics are unweighted. P values are test for heterogeneity (not for trend) from unadjusted differences in median (Kruskal-Wallis test) and chi-squared tests. Note that given that PTFQI was associated with diabetes cross-sectionally, after excluding diabetic patients the trend with glucose spuriously appears to be reversed in this baseline subsample.

Supplementary Table 2: Incidence of type 2 diabetes and related conditions across PTFQI quartiles in euthyroid participants.

	PTFQI quartiles				p trend	LF	HF
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th			
	[min.,-0.19)	[-0.19,0.00)	[0.00,0.22)	[0.22,max.]			
N	485	567	591	572		137	190
Person-years	2575	3000	3092	3038		726	987
<u>Type 2 diabetes</u>							
n	19	28	21	30		6	9
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	77.0	97.4	70.0	105.0		91.5	91.8
IRR (model 1)	1.00	1.66	1.48	1.72	0.060		
	(reference)	(1.01, 2.77)	(0.86, 2.55)	(1.06, 2.86)			
IRR (model 2)	1.00	1.38	1.32	1.35	0.331		
	(reference)	(0.84, 2.32)	(0.77, 2.27)	(0.83, 2.25)			
<u>Diabetes medication</u>							
n	14	19	19	21		4	8
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	57.0	64.9	63.3	72.3		61.4	81.1
IRR (model 1)	1.00	1.50	1.80	1.61	0.097		
	(reference)	(0.83, 2.76)	(1.00, 3.33)	(0.91, 2.93)			
IRR (model 2)	1.00	1.23	1.60	1.23	0.402		
	(reference)	(0.68, 2.27)	(0.88, 2.95)	(0.69, 2.25)			

Incidence rates weighted for loss to follow-up. Ratio estimations from Poisson regression models, weighted for loss to follow-up. Model 1 adjusted for age and sex, model 2 additionally adjusted for BMI. P trend calculated entering PTFQI quartile as a continuous variable. Incidence rates in non-euthyroid participants appear classified in “Low function” (LF) and “High function” (HF) groups, according to the table below
PTFQI: Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate Ratio.

<u>Type 2 diabetes</u>			
n/N (group)	Low fT4	Normal fT4	High fT4
High TSH	1/19 (Low function)	3/48 (Low function)	0
Normal TSH	1/67 (Low function)	98/2215 (Euthyroid)	4/39 (High function)
Low TSH	1/3 (Low function)	3/129 (High function)	2/22 (High function)

Supplementary Table 3: Incidence of type 2 diabetes across TSHI quartiles.

	TSHI quartiles				p trend
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	
	[min.,1.30)	[1.30,1.70)	[1.70,2.08)	[2.08,max.]	
N	636	635	635	636	
Person-years	3345	3350	3359	3365	
<u>Type 2 diabetes</u>					
n	24	34	26	29	
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	74.9	106.1	80.1	91.9	
IRR (model 1)	1.00	1.60	1.33	1.80	0.034
	(reference)	(1.02, 2.52)	(0.82, 2.16)	(1.14, 2.89)	
IRR (model 2)	1.00	1.47	1.16	1.57	0.149
	(reference)	(0.94, 2.33)	(0.72, 1.88)	(0.98, 2.51)	

Incidence rates weighted for loss to follow-up. Ratio estimations from Poisson regression models, weighted for loss to follow-up. Model 1 adjusted for age and sex, model 2 additionally adjusted for BMI. P trend calculated entering the index quartile as a continuous variable.

TSHI: TSH Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate

Supplementary Table 4: Incidence of type 2 diabetes across TT4RI quartiles.

	TT4RI quartiles				p trend
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	
	[min.,7.8)	[7.8,11.4)	[11.4,16.4)	[16.4,max.]	
N	636	635	635	636	
Person-years	3346	3348	3346	3380	
<u>Type 2 diabetes</u>					
n	31	28	29	25	
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	95.1	88.4	90.7	78.7	
IRR (model 1)	1.00	1.25	1.29	1.36	0.175
	(reference)	(0.80, 1.94)	(0.83, 2.00)	(0.86, 2.15)	
IRR (model 2)	1.00	1.36	1.28	1.20	0.441
	(reference)	(0.87, 2.13)	(0.82, 2.00)	(0.75, 1.90)	

Incidence rates weighted for loss to follow-up. Ratio estimations from Poisson regression models, weighted for loss to follow-up. Model 1 adjusted for age and sex, model 2 additionally adjusted for BMI. P trend calculated entering the index quartile as a continuous variable.

TT4RI: Thyrotroph T4 Resistance Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate Ratio.

Supplementary Table 5: Baseline characteristics of the sample after exclusion of baseline type 1 and type 2 diabetes and lost-to-follow-up (abnormal HbA1c excluded at baseline).

	All	PTFQI quartiles				p
		1 st [min.,-0.19)	2 nd [-0.19,0.00)	3 rd [0.00,0.22)	4 th [0.22,max.]	
N	2478	615	622	622	619	
ft4 (pmol/L)	14.20(2.12)	12.77(1.23)	13.85(2.76)	14.41(1.52)	15.76(1.34)	-
ft4 (ng/dL)	1.10(0.16)	0.99(0.10)	1.08(0.21)	1.12(0.12)	1.22(0.10)	-
TSH (mIU/L)	1.10(2.77)	0.54(0.28)	1.21(5.00)	1.28(2.12)	1.34(0.74)	-
Age (years)	47.5(15.1)	48.8(14.1)	47.5(15.1)	48.1(15.4)	45.4(15.6)	<0.001
Sex (male)	49.64[1,230]	53.66[330]	47.59[296]	50.32[313]	47.01[291]	0.077
Waist circumference (cm)	87.80(13.60)	88.32(12.96)	87.19(13.62)	87.96(13.42)	87.73(14.35)	0.400
BMI (Kg/m²)	26.84(4.53)	26.80(4.25)	26.52(4.30)	26.85(4.50)	27.20(5.03)	0.159
Glucose (spot) (mmol/L)	5.30(0.64)	5.34(0.73)	5.30(0.78)	5.32(0.73)	5.26(0.72)	0.024
HbA1c (%)	5.21(0.54)	5.24(0.54)	5.19(0.55)	5.23(0.53)	5.20(0.53)	0.316

Cells show mean(sd) or percentage[count]. Statistics are unweighted. P values are test for heterogeneity (not for trend) from unadjusted differences in median (Kruskal-Wallis test) and chi-squared tests. Note that given that PTFQI was associated with diabetes cross-sectionally, after excluding diabetic patients the trend with glucose spuriously appears to be reversed in this baseline subsample.

This table is similar to Supplementary Table 5, but excluding abnormal HbA1c at baseline.

Supplementary Table 6: Incidence of undetected type 2 diabetes (abnormal HbA1c at follow-up, not previously clinically detected) across PTFQI quartiles (abnormal HbA1c excluded at baseline).

	PTFQI quartiles				p trend
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	
	[min.,-0.19)	[-0.19,0.00)	[0.00,0.22)	[0.22,max.]	
N	615	622	622	619	
Person-years	3262	3289	3253	3277	
<u>Undetected type 2 diabetes</u>					
n	14	15	13	7	
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	42.9	45.6	40.0	21.4	
IRR (model 1)	1.00	1.44	1.55	0.77	0.799
	(reference)	(0.77, 2.73)	(0.80, 2.98)	(0.33, 1.65)	
IRR (model 2)	1.00	1.19	1.22	0.62	0.353

Incidence rates weighted for loss to follow-up. Ratio estimations from Poisson regression models, weighted for loss to follow-up. Model 1 adjusted for age and sex, model 2 additionally adjusted for BMI. P trend calculated entering PTFQI quartile as a continuous variable.

PTFQI: Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate Ratio.

This table is similar to Table 2 in the main text, but excluding abnormal HbA1c at baseline and observing undetected type 2 diabetes (abnormal HbA1c at follow-up, not previously clinically detected).

Supplementary Table 7: Incidence of type 2 diabetes and related conditions across PTFQI quartiles: additional models.

	PTFQI quartiles				p trend
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	
	[min.,-0.19)	[-0.19,0.00)	[0.00,0.22)	[0.22,max.]	
N	636	635	637	634	
Person-years	3369	3360	3329	3361	
<u>Type 2 diabetes</u>					
n	24	30	24	35	
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	74.0	93.3	73.7	111.5	
IRR (model 3)	1.00	1.14	1.29	1.59	0.031
	(reference)	(0.71, 1.83)	(0.79, 2.13)	(1.02, 2.52)	
IRR (model 4)	1.00	1.19	1.17	1.60	0.050
	(reference)	(0.75, 1.91)	(0.70, 1.93)	(1.02, 2.54)	
<u>Diabetes medication</u>					
n	17	21	21	26	
Incidence (/10⁴ py)	52.3	64.3	64.3	82.0	
IRR (model 3)	1.00	1.05	1.53	1.63	0.029
	(reference)	(0.60, 1.86)	(0.88, 2.70)	(0.97, 2.80)	
IRR (model 4)	1.00	1.14	1.37	1.65	0.050
	(reference)	(0.65, 2.01)	(0.77, 2.45)	(0.97, 2.85)	

Incidence rates weighted for loss to follow-up. Ratio estimations from Poisson regression models, weighted for loss to follow-up. Model 3 adjusted for age, sex, and waist circumference. Model 4 adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and total cholesterol. P trend calculated entering PTFQI quartile as a continuous variable.

PTFQI: Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate Ratio.

Supplementary Figure 1. Flowchart of participants' selection

Supplementary Figure 2. Scatterplot of thyrotropin (TSH) vs free thyroxine (fT4) and Barplot of crude type 2 diabetes incidence rates across intervals of parametric thyroid feedback quantile-based index (PTFQI) (abnormal HbA1c excluded at baseline).

Scatterplot: Dots represent observations. Red dots represent participants who developed type 2 diabetes during follow-up. Grey dashed vertical and horizontal straight lines mark fT4 and TSH normality ranges. Black dashed curves represent the 12.5th, 25th, 37.5th, 50th, 62.5th, 75th, and 87.5th percentiles of PTFQI dividing the sample in 8 equal parts. Inner plot: The bar height and the number at the base show crude type 2 diabetes incidence rates (weighted for loss to follow-up) for each PTFQI interval in cases per 10⁴ person-years. The widths of the bars are proportional to the fraction of the population at risk in each bar so that the area of the bar is proportional to the absolute number of cases (i.e., the count of red dots in the scatterplot). Central bars have been fused for visualization purposes (original bars as dashed ghost-bars) because the interval limits are numerically very close to the median and the incidence difference between them conveyed little meaningful information about the association.

N, number of participants; fT4, free Thyroxine; TSH, Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone; PTFQI, Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index; P *number*, Percentile *number*.

This figure is similar to the scatterplot in the main text, but excluding abnormal HbA1c at baseline.

Supplementary Figure 3. Type 2 diabetes incidence rate ratios of one unit increase of parametric thyroid feedback quantile-based index (PTFQI) across obesity strata (abnormal HbA1c excluded at baseline).

Estimations from a single Poisson regression model with PTFQI as a continuous variable, interaction terms with obesity strata, adjusted for age and sex, and weighted for loss to follow-up. Risk of normal weight participants at lower PTFQI is used as reference. PTFQI: Parametric Thyroid Feedback Quantile-based Index; n/N: number of new cases/number at risk; IRR: Incidence Rate Ratio.

This figure is similar to the Figure 2 in the main text, but excluding abnormal HbA1c at baseline.